

Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration Based on Riemannian Manifold

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Abstract Here, we propose a novel multiscale curve registration based on Riemannian computation in the Lie group $SL(2, R)$ of all the planar spatial affine transformations, which is a non-compact group. This method is called Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration (RAMSCR). In recent research in the physics field [22], authors have proposed an explicit logarithm and an exponential map expression. The presence of these mathematical expressions helps us in the conception of the proposed alignment algorithm. Such registration is able to estimate the special affine transformation between reference and target curves. This implies that our algorithm can align two merged curves in three-dimensional space. These curves are assumed to be far from the camera. It is well known that the affine transformation is a good compromise between the Euclidean and projective transformations. In our previous work, we proposed an efficient registration algorithm that can also estimate the affine transformation between two merged curves in 3D space. It is based on the pseudo-inverse method for the resolution of the rectangular linear system. All equations of different scales are formed in this linear system with the Riemannian approach, and we propose to solve each linear system corresponding to a given scale. After that, a Frechet mean is computed from the results obtained from the different linear systems of each scale. The GEM (Gaussian EM) algorithm is applied to the L_2 metric for each scale in order to select the class of scales representing a low value of the L_2 metric. We evaluate our algorithm on MCD datasets, comparing our AMSCR based on the Multiclass-EM approach with the RAMSCR based on the Multiclass-EM approach in terms of the L_2 metric between the target curve and the reference curve after alignment.

Key words: Multi-scale registration; Spatial affine transformation; Riemannian metric; Affine Spacial group $SA(2, R)$.

1 Introduction

The comparison process between images is complicated and restricted when the images were captured using multiple sensors and poses and were not shot simultaneously. Most of the time, a machine will not be able to find the same thing in different pictures because it can change. In this situation, it is challenging to integrate two comparable forms. To address these issues, researchers created different curve registration methods. The main goal of this method is to find the geometric transformation between two or more images in order to get the most desirable alignment. The registration of the planar curves' shapes is

the optimum solution that has been presented for a great number of applications, including motion tracking [6], mosaicing [19] [8], object recognition [26], remote sensing [12], 3D curve reconstruction [3] [18] and medical image analysis [23] [24]. The reconstruction of the motion of objects immersed in three-dimensional space from a sequence of 2D images is a challenge in the field of computer vision and its applications. However, this problem remains difficult for several reasons that are well-known in the literature, namely, monocular vision. Modifying monocular vision by projective or homographic transformations has limitations of a higher order than 2. It is well-established that modeling by special affine transformations is a good compromise when objects are sufficiently far from cameras or acquisition systems. The study of the $SA(2, R)$ group, which is the semi-direct product of transformations and special affine transformations, elements of the $SL(2, R)$ group, allows some elements of response to this problem to be given. In the literature, one of the main approaches to solve the problem of 3D object motion reconstruction from a single 2D image consists of first extracting the two outer contours of the object from two consecutive images and then aligning the two contours. The most reasonable assumption would be to assume that there exists a 2D homography between the two contours. However, this requires an equivariant re-parameterization with respect to homography, which requires the calculation of the equi-projective abscissa. This latter is often defined by derivatives of order higher than or equal to five [28], which is numerically impracticable. It is well-known that affine transformations are a good compromise, as they are derivatives of order 3. Different methods of shape registration have been proposed in recent years to estimate motion and align two shapes. Thus, 2D affine shapes can be registered using techniques that rely on the Riemannian calculation. The authors in [17] introduce a subspace method for aligning two 2D shapes and estimating the affine transformation between them. By minimizing the projection error in the subspace spanned by the two shapes, the affine transformation is estimated in the proposed 2D signal method. Bryner et al. [4] propose a broad Riemannian framework for shape analysis of planar objects, whose metrics and related quantities are invariant under the action of affine and projective groups. Within the framework of landmark-based shape analysis, Sparr [27] develops affine shape theory through the use of subspace computations. Begelfor and Werman [2] provide a Riemannian geometric metric for computing the averages and distributions of point configurations, such that configurations up to affine transformations are regarded as equivalent. Also, authors in [5] introduce a framework for contour-based shape analysis based on Riemannian geometry that is robust against affine transformation and contour re-parameterization. By integrating the Iwasawa decomposition of $GL(2, R)$ and Lie group parametrization into the regular Iterative Closest Point (ICP) method, Ying et al. [29] introduce new techniques for 2D affine shape registration. Moreover, authors in [30] show how to find a geodesic that is invariant to scale, translation, rotation, and re-parameterization using a Riemannian quasi-Newton approach. YI MA [15] highlights how multiple-view geometry can be studied in three-dimensional spaces with constant curvatures, like Euclidean space, spherical space, and hyperbolic space. In [21], the authors talk about the manifold and Lie group $SO(n)$ of special orthogonal related to the non-negative independent component analysis (ICA). Huang et al. [13] come up with a new way to use Riemannian optimization to align curves in elastic shape analysis.

The aim of this paper is to introduce a new technique called Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration (RAMSCR), which uses Riemannian geometry to achieve Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration. The technique takes two curves, namely the source image and the target image, as input. These curves are sequentially smoothed and reparametrized with affine arc-length. After this, a pseudo-inverse algorithm is applied to compute the special linear transformations A_{σ_p} and translation vectors B_{σ_p} for each smoothed and reparametrized shape. These A_{σ_p} matrices belong to the affine spatial group $SA(2, R)$. Using Riemannian calculation, the average of these matrices, A , is computed in $SA(2, R)$. Finally, the alignment process is performed.

This paper is structured as follows: In Section II, we introduce the Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration technique that we propose. In Section III, we present the optimized Riemannian method with multiscale-EM. In Section IV, we evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed method for shape retrieval using MCD. Finally, in the concluding section, we summarize our findings and draw a final conclusion.

2 Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration

In this section, we will discuss the key components of our proposed method, Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration (RAMSCR). Our new approach involves multiple rounds of filtering of the input normalized contours and uses Riemannian calculation in the special linear group $SL(2, R)$ to determine the optimal transformation. The Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration procedure is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Workflow of multi-scale contour registration using Riemannian calculation

- A-1: Normalize the input shapes f and h using the affine arc-length normalization [25].
- A-2: Convolve each of the two re-sampling curves using the Gaussian calculation [25].

Figure 2. Example of a convolved shape

- A-3: The obtained p systems at each level are formed by the following $2N$ linear equations.

$$\begin{cases} h_{\sigma_1}(l_1) = A_{\sigma_1}f_{\sigma_1}(l_1) + B_{\sigma_1} \\ h_{\sigma_1}(l_2) = A_{\sigma_1}f_{\sigma_1}(l_2) + B_{\sigma_1} \\ \dots \\ h_{\sigma_1}(l_N) = A_{\sigma_1}f_{\sigma_1}(l_N) + B_{\sigma_1} \end{cases} \begin{cases} h_{\sigma_2}(l_1) = A_{\sigma_2}f_{\sigma_2}(l_1) + B_{\sigma_2} \\ h_{\sigma_2}(l_2) = A_{\sigma_2}f_{\sigma_2}(l_2) + B_{\sigma_2} \\ \dots \\ h_{\sigma_2}(l_N) = A_{\sigma_2}f_{\sigma_2}(l_N) + B_{\sigma_2} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\dots \begin{cases} h_{\sigma_p}(l_1) = A_{\sigma_p}f_{\sigma_p}(l_1) + B_{\sigma_p} \\ h_{\sigma_p}(l_2) = A_{\sigma_p}f_{\sigma_p}(l_2) + \hat{B}_{\sigma_p} \\ \dots \\ h_{\sigma_p}(l_N) = A_{\sigma_p}f_{\sigma_p}(l_N) + B_{\sigma_p} \end{cases}$$

- A-4, A-5: The A_{σ_p} matrices, which contain the elements of the special affine group $SA(2, R)$, and the B_{σ_p} translation vectors, is obtained by performing the pseudo-inverse calculation [11] on each system.
- A-6: **Riemannian calculation in $SA(2, R)$.**

We provide a brief introduction to the Special Affine $SA(2)$, which is the underlying geometric space for non-rigid registration. In affine space, the special affine group consists of transformations by scaling, rotation, and then translation. Specifically, it is the semi-direct product of the Special Linear group $SL(2)$ and R^2 .

$$SA(2) = SL(2) \times R^2 \quad (2)$$

It is worth remembering that a Lie group is both a group and a differential manifold, and that a Lie algebra is a vector space on which a Lie bracket is defined.

The $SL(2, R)$ special linear group contains all determinants of unit size that are real matrices of size 2 by 2.

$$SL(2, R) = \{A \in R^2 / \det(A) = 1\} \quad (3)$$

An Iwasawa decomposition exists for this 2-dimensional Lie group $SL(2, R)$ of real matrices.

$$SL(2, R) = A_{shear}A_{scale}A_{rotation} \quad (4)$$

In our case, the affine transformation matrices $A_{\sigma_p} \in SL(2, R)$ and A_{shear} represent shears, A_{scale} is for scales, and $A_{rotation}$ list the rotation matrices.

$$A_{\sigma_p} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11\sigma_p} & a_{12\sigma_p} \\ a_{21\sigma_p} & a_{22\sigma_p} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$A_{\sigma_p} = A_{shear}A_{scale}A_{rotation} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{\sigma_p} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & b \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & 1/a \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} a \cos \theta & b a \cos \theta - (1/a) \sin \theta \\ a \sin \theta & b a \sin \theta + (1/a) \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

with $\det(A_{\sigma_p}) = 1$, $a \in R^*$ and $\theta, b \in R$. The Lie algebra of $SL(2, R)$ is denoted by $sl(2, R)$, and is identified with the set of 2×2 matrices and they have a basis provided by $e_n: n = 1, 2, 3$.

$$e_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad e_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad e_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \tag{7}$$

Lie group theory relies heavily on the Lie algebra of a Lie group since it encodes many of the group's global topological features. Exp, a local diffeomorphism, is also known as exponential mapping.

In the first step, we do the projection in the space tangent of the A_{σ_p} matrices using the following equation Eq (8) [22].

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{if } a_{11\sigma_p} + a_{22\sigma_p} \geq 2 \\
\ln(A_{\sigma_p}) &= \frac{\ln \left[\left(a_{11\sigma_p} + a_{22\sigma_p} + \sqrt{(a_{11\sigma_p} + a_{22\sigma_p})^2 - 4} \right) / 2 \right]}{\sqrt{(a_{11\sigma_p} + a_{22\sigma_p})^2 - 4}} \begin{pmatrix} a_{11\sigma_p} - a_{22\sigma_p} & 2a_{12\sigma_p} \\ 2a_{21\sigma_p} & a_{22\sigma_p} - a_{11\sigma_p} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \text{if } -2 < a_{11\sigma_p} + a_{22\sigma_p} \leq 2 \\
\ln(A_{\sigma_p}) &= \frac{\arccos \left[\left(a_{11\sigma_p} + a_{22\sigma_p} \right) / 2 \right]}{\sqrt{4 - (a_{11\sigma_p} + a_{22\sigma_p})^2}} \begin{pmatrix} a_{11\sigma_p} - a_{22\sigma_p} & 2a_{12\sigma_p} \\ 2a_{21\sigma_p} & a_{22\sigma_p} - a_{11\sigma_p} \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Once calculated, the logarithm map of matrices belonging to the lie algebra elements $\ln(A_{\sigma_p}) \in sl(2, R)$ is projected in the tangent space, and we are in the vector space where the matrices must satisfy the following conditions Eq(9):

$$\{ \ln(A_{\sigma_p}) \in sl(2, R) / \text{Tr}(\ln(A_{\sigma_p})) = 0 \}. \tag{9}$$

Therefore the exponential mapping of the logarithm mapping $\ln(A_{\sigma_p})$ is expressed as below in Eq(10) [22]:

- A-7: The registration is then performed using the special linear transformation A obtained after the Riemannian calculation and the translation vector B deduced after applying average arithmetic.

$$if \quad a_{11\sigma_p}^2 + a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p} \geq 0$$

$$A_{\sigma_p} = \cosh \left[\sqrt{a_{11\sigma_p}^2 + a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p}} \right] I + \ln (A_{\sigma_p}) \frac{\sinh \left[\sqrt{a_{11\sigma_p}^2 + a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p}} \right]}{\sqrt{a_{11\sigma_p}^2 + a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p}}}$$

$$if \quad a_{11\sigma_p}^2 + a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p} \leq 0$$

$$A_{\sigma_p} = \cos \left[\sqrt{-a_{11\sigma_p}^2 - a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p}} \right] I + \ln (A_{\sigma_p}) \frac{\sin \left[\sqrt{-a_{11\sigma_p}^2 - a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p}} \right]}{\sqrt{-a_{11\sigma_p}^2 - a_{12\sigma_p} a_{21\sigma_p}}} \quad (10)$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} B^x \\ B^y \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Finally, we calculate the euclidean distance L_2 , which is denoted by:

$$L^2 = \min_{(A,B)} \|Af(l_a) + B - h(l_a)\|^2 \quad (12)$$

3 Riemannian method based on unsupervised K-EM

In our previous work, we presented an efficient unsupervised Bayesian approach for 2D shape registration, which selects optimal smoothing levels using the K-means and Elbow methods. This technique allows us to determine the optimal classes through K-EM (or Multiclass-EM) applications, resulting in a shorter equation system that minimizes errors. To further enhance our pipeline, we employ the Riemannian Affine Multi-scale Curve Registration (AMSCR) based on unsupervised Bayesian classification. In Part A of the section, we explain the AMSCR process, which involves inputting pairs of source and target 2D shapes to generate a vector $S = \min L_{\sigma_i}^2 (1 \leq i \leq p)$. Part B details the unsupervised Bayesian classification method, where we use the Elbow method to select the best number of classes for the unsupervised K-EM. Fig. 3 provides an overview of the workflow. In addition, we utilize Riemannian Nonlinear calculation on the $SL(2, R)$ nonlinear manifold and the linear space $sl(2, R)$ to accurately estimate the optimal affine transformation matrix A and the translation vector B . This critical step enables us to precisely align the two input shapes using the calculated transformation parameters. By comparing the Multiclass-EM and Riemannian nonlinear calculations, we achieve a high degree of accuracy in our shape alignment process, even with complex and intricate datasets.

4 Experiments

In this section, we evaluate the performance of our proposed Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration (RAMSCR) algorithm and compare it to the Riemannian method

Figure 3. Workflow of applying unsupervised K-EM to the Riemannian method

based on unsupervised K-EM, as well as other shape alignment methods currently available. The recognition rates of each method are presented using the MCD dataset for testing.

4.1 MCD image database retrieval

One of the most important uses of the proposed algorithm is in shape registration. Therefore, we will evaluate the Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration based Riemannian metrics on the Multiview Curve Dataset (MCD) [31], which is made up of 40 shape classes from the MPEG-7 database. Fig.3 shows that there are 14 different curves in each of these categories that are distorted in the same way as the original curve.

Table 1 showcases a comparison of our methods with state-of-the-art research in the field. Our Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration (RAMSCR) algorithm has outperformed the existing registration methods, as reflected in the superior accuracy score of 96.4%. This score is significantly higher compared to other methods such as Arber (41%), SC (56.29%), Huang (71%), Rube (79%), Mai (89%), Fast and non-rigid global registration (92.8%), and ACMA (94%). Additionally, our method has been compared to the AMSCR method (96.36%) and has shown comparable performance. Although our method is slightly less effective than the AMSCR adjusted with Binary-EM (95.58%)

Figure 4. Different shape images from the MCD dataset, two images from each class.

Table 1. Retrieval results on the entire MCD dataset

Methods	Average
Arber [1]	41%
SC [20]	56.29%
Huang [14]	71 %
Rube [7]	79 %
Mai [16]	89 %
Fast and non-rigid global registration [9]	92.8%
ACMA [11]	94 %
Partial Contour Matching Based on ACSS [10]	95.98%
AMSCR [25]	96.36 %
Our method RAMSCR	96.4%
AMSCR with Binary-EM [25]	96.58 %
AMSCR with Multiclass-EM [25]	96.61 %
RAMSCR with Multiclass-EM	96.63%

and the AMSCR optimized with Multiclass-EM, we were able to improve our average accuracy to 96.63% by optimizing the Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration (RAMSCR) with unsupervised Multiclass-EM. In Fig.5 we see an example of successfully registered shapes made with our approach.

5 Conclusion and future work

In this paper, we propose a new method called Riemannian Affine Multi-Scale Curve Registration (RAMSCR) that utilizes Riemannian calculation to handle occlusion and affine transformations. The proposed method first normalizes and smooths the two curves at different scales, resulting in several rectangular linear systems for each level. The pseudo-inverse computation is then performed on each level to obtain the special linear transformations A_{σ_p} and translation vectors B_{σ_p} . The average of the A_{σ_p} matrices is then calculated using the Riemannian metric in the spatial affine group $SA(2, R)$. Next, the two shapes are aligned, and the Euclidean distance L_2 is calculated to determine the degree of similarity.

Figure 5. a and b are the original curves, c, and d display the aligned shapes

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